

IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF THE LESSON THROUGH DIDACTIC GAMES IN MATHEMATICS CLASSES IN ELEMENTARY GRADES

Mirzabayev Yuldoshali Abdumannonovich
teacher of FerSU

It is particularly difficult to teach the basics of science, especially mathematics, to students of junior school age. In particular, teaching mathematics to children enrolled in the first grade creates difficulties for the teacher. Because the levels of preparation for mastering the concepts of mathematics of the first graders are different from each other. Some children come from pre-school groups of kindergartens, some come directly from families. Those who come from families also have different levels of preparation. Children from families with a positive attitude toward learning have a stronger interest in learning mathematics.

The diversity of children's knowledge and their interest in mastering science creates a number of difficulties in educational work with young students.

Didactic games, cooperation between children when the whole class participates, self-control, concentration, coordination, quick understanding and answering questions will be of great importance in the formation of quick response and other educational qualities. Such didactic games reduce the attitude of the student towards the teacher. As a result, the teacher becomes a friend to the child, a partner in solving this or that issue. The main goal of any didactic games used in mathematics lessons is educational.

Education is a planned process of conscious assimilation and strengthening of knowledge, skills and abilities given to students in the course of the lesson.

It can be used at any stage of the lesson, depending on the level of knowledge and interests of the students of the class, depending on the content and structure of

the mathematics lesson, giving great importance to its size.

Didactic games, in terms of their form, are different from creative games that are played mainly in kindergarten, as well as games that the teacher himself explains by telling a story and that is reinforced by asking students one by one. It is completely different from games. Didactic games serve the purpose of teaching and are conducted at an interesting, fun, and comprehensible level. Children train with all their heart in order to win, they get used to completing every given task without fail, as a result, their interest in doing didactic tasks increases. Didactic games help to better understand the purpose of each lesson, the goals and tasks of each exercise.

Didactic games include the visualization of education, the teacher's speech and children's actions, as a result of which unity is born in perception (sight, hearing, skin sensation signs). This allows the children to think about what the teacher said and express what was said, that is, the students themselves fulfill the rules of the didactic games. Structural features of didactic games provide an opportunity to analyze students' activities. That is why all children act with interest during the game.

Didactic games affect the child's emotions and form a positive attitude and interest in learning. Children play the game with great pleasure. and they wait impatiently for the start of the game, involuntarily the joyful scene of tomorrow's school day is embodied in their minds.

We know that children don't grow only by reading, but they also learn to be harmonious and learn to know life in the process of playing.

It should be emphasized that children learn self-control and self-control in these games. These games make children disciplined.

Experience shows that didactic games help to cultivate unity and discipline, because each game is related to the desire to win, and requires strict and consistent compliance with the terms and rules of the game. is enough. When playing games such as "Who is more accurate and faster", "Don't come empty",

"The best accountant", "Dictation to remember what you saw", students should be quiet in the classroom. they will be able to control themselves, climb up to the blackboard on tiptoe without making a sound, return to their seats calmly, listen carefully to sounds, look at numbers carefully.

References

1. Hisoblash malakalarini shakllantirish. //Boshlang'ich ta'lim, 2010. – №3, 26-27-betlar
2. Boshlang'ich ta'lim o'quvchilarida inovasion faoliyat ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirish yo'llari. //Uzluksiz ta'lim, 2010. – №3 46-49-betlar.
13. Tadjiyev Z.G. Boshlang'ich sinf matematika darslarida tarixiy materiallardan foydalanish. – T., 1981. – 149-bet.

